

THE IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND METHODS OF ITS IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract: This article describes the issues of entrepreneurship and the application of the marketing concept in the enterprises of our country.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, economy, marketing, enterprise, business, market, leader, production, price, product, consumer, advertising, commodity, buyer, competition.

After the independence of our republic, opportunities were created for the development, reform and liberalization of the economy. Initiatives were taken in the expansion of the private sector, small business, farms, and the rapid development of entrepreneurship. Today, the share of small business (business) in the gross domestic product is 54%. This was largely due to the strengthening of the legal framework, the creation of a system of concessions and loans for this sector of the economy. As the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov noted:

I would like to pay special attention to the work being done to diversify the products produced in our country. Diversification of production creates additional opportunities to attract investments and allows local enterprises to compete in domestic and foreign markets based on the rational use of financial resources.

S.S. Ghulomov, Yo.A. Abdullaev, V.B. Berkinov, B.Yu. Khodiev and others are engaged. Including, S.S. Ghulomov's —Entrepreneurship and small business, Small business management by B. Yukhodiev, M.S. Kasimova and others, Shodibekova D.A., M.S. Kasimova and others. M.R. The formation and development of small business, small business organizational forms, planning, licensing, management psychology, small business financial situation and credit provision, marketing features of small business were considered in the manuals of "Small business and cooperation" by

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Boltaboev and others. It is known that in the conditions of market economy and free competition, marketing comes to the fore. Because marketing is a process that marks the way of the product from the producer to the consumer. Product development is a complex system of mediation, based on a comprehensive study of the needs and demands of the buyer. This process is a system of adapting to a changing market. The marketing approach to production and general management includes aspects of influencing the customer. The marketing department should be considered as the main link that connects all other departments and leads the production. As a result of their joint cooperation, the market is researched, new business opportunities of the enterprise are searched, marketing strategy and tactics are created, concrete measures are developed for the movement of advertising goods, prices are implemented, plans are created and their implementation is monitored. One of the most important tasks of marketing is to organize and facilitate the production of guaranteed high-quality, competitive products that meet customer demand. Here, one of the elements of marketing in the management of the economy is the incomparable role of advertising. A well-organized advertisement allows to manage the market demand in the market conditions and the buyer's minimum. For this purpose, advertising attracts the attention of the general public to any product or service of the enterprise or social activity. Each enterprise and organization develops its own advertising program based on the type of product and its level of popularity.

Establishing the main elements of marketing - market research and analysis, pricing principles; service policy - with Cyrus McCormick will be connected. Since 1902, the universities of the USA (Michigan, California, Illinois) have introduced subjects on marketing issues ("Product marketing", "Marketing styles" and others), and started giving lectures. In 1926, the National Marketing Association was established in the USA.

Later, on its basis, the American Marketing Society was founded, which was renamed the American Marketing Association in 1973. A little later, such associations and organizations appeared in Western European countries and Japan. International marketing organizations - The European Marketing and Social Thought Research Society, the International Marketing Federation, the European Academy, and the like appeared. In the middle of the 60s of the last century, all the largest American

corporations began to apply the basic requirements of marketing in their economic activities.

In Western Europe and Japan, marketing ideas were introduced more slowly than in the USA. But by the end of the 1960s, they began to rapidly master marketing practices and made significant progress. According to the American model, marketing activities are focused on achieving the company's goals and objectives, and secondly on satisfying the needs of consumers. According to the Japanese model, marketing activities should first of all satisfy the wants and needs of consumers. The main goal of Japanese marketing is to serve consumers, and for American marketing, all means can be used to achieve the goal.

The era of modern marketing began in 1995 of the last century. Since then, marketing has been studied as a complex social-economic process.

Currently, there are many research firms working on marketing issues in the USA and developed countries. Also, universities, trade industry associations, government organizations and services have started to study marketing issues based on commercial management. In 1972, F. Kotler founded the concepts of micromarketing and macromarketing. In 1976, Shelby Hunt showed that marketing is a science of the exchange process. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, the process of globalization of marketing was observed. Also, in 1990, an international conference on global marketing was held in Canberra, Australia, under the motto "Marketing is global", "Marketing means business". Currently, the industrial age is giving way to the information age in the world economy. It is observed in all developed countries of the world. Rapidly changing market conditions, demands of the market. Bill Gates's book "Business at the speed of thought" states that the use of modern information technologies allows us to anticipate the situation in the market not a few weeks, but a few hours in advance, and allows us to achieve the speed necessary to maintain high competitiveness in the market. Regarding the competitors, the idea that "whoever forgets his competitors, forgets the market" should not be ignored. Today, competitors are not to be destroyed, but to be respected, because they encourage thinking, creativity, and aspiration, rather than snoozing.

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